

(1) Title and Details

(A) Title

Faris-Penrose Diagram, Faris-Penrose-Hawking Singularity Theory and Faris-Penrose-Stuart Consciousness Theory

(B) Author Information

1. **Author Name:** Mirza Faris Ahmad

2. **Author Affiliation:** Bahria Town School and College, Lahore, Pakistan

3. **Author Email:** tf16375283@gmail.com

(2) Short Summary

Penrose Diagram is actually finite 2D Picture of infinite 4D spacetime. I reproduced same results using my mechanics (Faris-Newton Classical Mechanics) by saying that spacetime events can happen in multiple velocity, multiple movements and multiple velocity-movement ways. Penrose Singularity theorem says that celestial objects that are collapsed have a thing called singularity. I said same thing that center of gravity is singularity indeed using my mechanics. Further Extension of Penrose Singularity Theorem the Penrose-Hawking Singularity Theorem says that big bang has itself a singularity. I said same thing using my mechanics that center of gravity of big bang is singularity of big bang indeed. The Orchestrated Objective Reduction Theory says that microtubule superposition state collapse is a cause of consciousness. I said through my theory (Quantum Reality) that microtubule superposition state is actually nothing but atom's layers observing the one from them or collapse using photon is actually consciousness.

(3) Keywords

(1) Penrose Diagram

(2) Faris-Penrose Diagram

(3) Penrose-Hawking Singularity Theorem

(4) Faris-Penrose-Hawking Singularity Theory

(5) Orchestrated Objective Reduction Theory

(6) Faris-Penrose-Stuart Consciousness Theory.

(4) Statements and Declarations

(A) Competing Interests

No, I declare that the authors have no competing interests or other interests that might be perceived to influence the results and/or discussion reported in this paper.

(B)Funding

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(C)Author Contribution

I am Mirza Faris Ahmad.The only Author and Researcher of this Research Paper.

(5)Penrose Diagram and Consciousness

(A)Introduction

Transformation of Penrose Diagram of spacetime to a simple one through Faris-Newton Classical Mechanics is named as Faris-Penrose Diagram,Transformation of Penrose Singularity Theorem and Penrose-Hawking Singularity Theorem through Faris-Newton Classical Mechanics is named as Faris-Penrose Singularity Theory and Faris-Penrose-Hawking Singularity Theory and Transformation of Orchestrated Objective Reduction Theory through Quantum reality Theory is named as Faris-Penrose-Stuart Consciousness Theory.

(B)Headings

1.Penrose Diagram

The Spacetime

Events in spacetime are specified by four coordinates.Imagine for a moment what a event is? how would you answer this question.To answer this consider for example that a event in spacetime happens in some way.

Types of events

1-Movement Way of Event or Movement Event

An event can happen in movement way means a object undergoing event can describe it's event as a movement one that is event's coordinates has a movement combination.

General Equation

$$(D_{(-n)})^t (r(t))$$

2-Velocity Way of Event or Velocity Event

An event can happen in velocity way means a object undergoing event can describe it's event as a velocity one that is event's coordinates has a velocity combination.

General Equation

$$(D_{(+n)})^t (r(t))$$

3-Movement-Velocity Way of Event or Movement-Velocity Event

An event can happen in movement-velocity way means a object undergoing event can describe it's event as a movement-velocity one that is event's coordinates has a movement-velocity combination.

General Equation

$$(D_{(+n)})^t (r(t))$$

Note:

All events types describes the same event happening in different ways four numbers separately are not useful since it is just like saying mass and velocity without saying momentum.

Mathematical Equation

$$(D_t)^n (r(t))$$

The above expression is a set of infinite expressions.

Note:

Elaborating the “Integral Derivative Operator w.r.t. t $((D_t)^n)$ ” more.Consider that + and - are written together in n along with number what this means is this that Integrals and derivatives are present in this single expression and that |n| is actually number of integral or derivatives but actually there are two numbers i.e. two '|n|' one for integral and another derivative.

The Faris-Penrose Diagram

Penrose Diagram just convert infinite 4D spacetime into Finite 2D picture of spacetime.The Faris-Penrose Diagram just convert 4D infinite spacetime into 2D finite or infinite Picture of spacetime so I reproduced same results using my Mechanics.

Explanation

Penrose Diagram uses the 4D infinite structure of spacetime itself and converts it to 2D space by bending the infinital property.I tried to do same thing using my Mechanics in which first I said that 4D spacetime undergoes events in three possible ways and these events are consisting of position function and time can be plotted on graph in a 2D way but graph is infinite but if you rotate the graph anticlockwise starting

from position function vertical axis and connect its head to the actual graph's time horizontal axis and the head of time axis of rotated graph to time axis head of actual graph you will get a box where you can plot even infinite function in square that is because infinity means that that part between box is not lined but coloured highlighting the infinity and the rotated graph is the same as the actual one since the axis is opposite of rotated graph from original one and that the rotated one is forming a box with actual hence this makes the rotated graph vectorially equal to first one both undergoing Lorentz coordinate transformation of special relativity.

2. Penrose Singularity Theorem and Hawking-Penrose Singularity Theorem

Penrose Singularity Theorem

Penrose Singularity Theorem said that black holes indeed have a central point called singularity and that point had infinite density interpreted afterwards by others.

Penrose-Hawking Singularity Theorem

Penrose Singularity Theorem said that big bang indeed have a central point called singularity.

Faris-Penrose Singularity Theory

I said that everything has its center of gravity as I told in Faris-Newton Gravitation Force Laws Equation but the fact that centre of gravity is actually the singularity of blackhole or a collapsed star is a thing is more simple in context. Here I am giving a general description about how a centre of gravity gives description about objects mass. In the Faris-Newton Universal Motion Theory (came out from Faris-Newton Classical Mechanics) on which I will write an article in future will describe whole reality each star rather than just description of Mass through centre of gravity.

Faris-Penrose-Hawking Singularity Theory

The Big bang is actually a centre of gravity of time and space or spacetime. Since gravity is a curvature of spacetime, this big bang's curvature is the first possible known spacetime curvature ever form. The more attraction one form the more bigger the universe or reality is coming out from nothing through gravity.

Note:

A Pause for appreciation

A Pause and special appreciation to Renhard Genzel and Andrea Ghez for their work on singularities and becoming a part of Nobel prize.

3.Orchestrated Objective Reduction Theory

The original theory says that microtubule superposition state collapse is a cause of consciousness.

Faris' Theory of Quantum System

This theory predicts quantum structures of each part of quantum reality and this happens when one uses a tensorial approach for representing a reaction of vector dissociation that reaction in which vector is dissociated into parts and initial form converts to final and the final vector is greater than initial one and that final vector can be again converted back to initial one since the reaction is reversible. The final vector is representing any part of quantum reality having different quantum structures. This is what the theory says and its main idea is.

As an example consider the vector dissociation increased vector equation for atom. The final increased vector is showing different quantum structures of atom.

Faris-Penrose-Stuart Consciousness Theory

I said that the quantum structures of each part of reality are actually the superposition state of microtubules cells' Atoms that are responsible for Consciousness.

A deeper insight:Explanation

To explain in more detail the objective reduction or state collapse happening in the microtubules of brain cells is actually a phenomenon explained by Faris' Quantum Reality Theory in the way that each state is a quantum structure all in superposition upon observation it collapsed as the microtubules cells's Atoms are in quantum structures superposition. This is what the Faris-Penrose-Stuart theory says so the main task is to find out quantum structures rather than solving the below equation.

Mathematical Equation

$$((\sum_{j=1}^n ((-h^2)/(2m) (\nabla_j)^2 - (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) (Ze^2)/(r_j)) + \frac{1}{2} (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) \sum_{j \neq k}^Z (e^2/(r_j - r_k)))_n (|\Psi\rangle) \cdot (\sum_{i=1}^q (((\sum_{j=1}^n ((-h^2)/(2m) (\nabla_j)^2 - (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) (Ze^2)/(r_j)) + \frac{1}{2} (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) \sum_{j \neq k}^Z (e^2/(r_j - r_k)))_n)_i) (|\theta\rangle) = ((\sum_{j=1}^n ((-h^2)/(2m) (\nabla_j)^2 - (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) (Ze^2)/(r_j)) + \frac{1}{2} (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) \sum_{j \neq k}^Z (e^2/(r_j - r_k)))_n ((\sum_{j=1}^n ((-h^2)/(2m) (\nabla_j)^2 - (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) (Ze^2)/(r_j)) + \frac{1}{2} (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) \sum_{j \neq k}^Z (e^2/(r_j - r_k)))_n$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& k \text{ to } Z) (e^2/(\lambda_j - \lambda_k)))^{(\alpha)} (\sum_{i=1}^q) (((\sum_{j=1}^n) ((-h^2)/(2m) (\nabla_j)^2 \\
& - (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) (Ze^2)/(r_j)) + \frac{1}{2} (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) \sum_{j \neq k \text{ to } Z) (e^2/(r_j - r_k)) \\
&)_{n_i}) \\
&) (\sum_{i=1}^q) (((\sum_{j=1}^n) ((-h^2)/(2m) (\nabla_j)^2 - (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) (Ze^2)/(r_j)) + \\
& \frac{1}{2} (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) \sum_{j \neq k \text{ to } Z) (e^2/(r_j - r_k)))^{(\beta)}_{i}) (\eta_{(\alpha\beta)}) + (m' h f) \\
& (\sum_{i=1}^q) (((\sum_{j=1}^n) ((-h^2)/(2m) (\nabla_j)^2 - (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) (Ze^2)/(r_j)) + \\
& \frac{1}{2} (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) \sum_{j \neq k \text{ to } Z) (e^2/(r_j - r_k)))_{n_i}) (\sum_{i=1}^q) (((\sum_{j=1}^n) \\
& ((-h^2)/(2m) (\nabla_j)^2 - (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) (Ze^2)/(r_j)) + \frac{1}{2} (1/(4\pi \epsilon_0)) \sum_{j \neq k \text{ to } \\
& Z) (e^2/(r_j - r_k)))^{(\beta)}_{i}) \\
&) \vec{e}(\beta)
\end{aligned}$$

Where I have not write full value of $|\theta\rangle, \nabla$ and $|\Psi\rangle$ since the equation has not known exact solution.

(C) Discussion It is important to note that as it is possible to construct a finite yet simple diagram of spacetime similar to Penrose Diagram hence it is possible to make simpler version of Penrose Diagram named Faris-Penrose Diagram.

It is possible to construct a simplified version of Penrose and Penrose-Hawking Singularity Theorems therefore these are known are Faris-Penrose and Faris-Penrose-Hawking Singularity Theory and similarly for Orchestrated Objective Reduction Theory.

(D) Importance

The importance of this is this that both of the diagram and 2 theories are very important since I reproduced Penrose results from my theories and diagrams in a much simpler way.

(E) Abbreviations

1. Faris-Penrose Diagram and Simplified Penrose Diagram are same.
 2. Faris-Penrose Singularity Theory and Simplified Faris-Penrose Singularity Theorem are same.
 3. Faris-Penrose-Hawking Singularity Theory and Simplified Penrose-Hawking Singularity Theorem are same.
 4. Orchestrated Objective Reduction Theory and Simplified Faris-Penrose-Stuart Consciousness Theory are the same.
- Note:** Adding a complex with all three theories and diagrams are synonymous to my theories and diagrams.
5. Orchestrated and Orchestrated refer to same word.

(F)Prediction

- 1.The match of center of gravity and singularity is a prediction of both theories of singularity.
- 2.The prediction of layers of atoms collapsing to consciousness.

(G)Conclusion

The Faris-Penrose Diagram, Faris-Penrose Singularity Theory and Faris-Penrose-Hawking Singularity Theory and Faris-Penrose-Stuart Consciousness Theory all 3 of them work the same way but in a simple manner.